

Date Accessed (of search)	Search (Search term used)	Origin of website (e.g. Knowledge of Researcher; found in X)	(Primary) Website	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health; Social)	High level finding (data we are interested in)	National; Regional or Cantonal	Experts Identified	Experts Note	New Website Identified	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health; Social Care; Education; Youth work etc. See list)	Note	New Website Identified - Used as search?
15.02.18	https://www.carsuk.org/wales/	Google Search 'young carers legal provisions England'	https://www.carersuk.org/wales	NGO	Carers organisations	Policy and research library	National	-	-	https://www.carsuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy	NGO	Carers organisations	Policy and research library	y
15.02.18	https://www.carsuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library	https://www.carersuk.org/wales	https://www.carersuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library	NGO	Carers organisations	Briefings and reports	National	-	-	https://www.carsuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library/carers-rights-and-entitlements-what-was-new-in-2017-and-what-s-changing-in-2018	NGO	Carers organisations	-	y
15.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	https://www.carsuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library/state-of-caring-in-wales-2017	NGO	Carers organisations	-	y
15.02.18	https://www.carsuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library/carers-rights-and-entitlements-what-was-new-in-2017-and-what-s-changing-in-2018	https://www.carersuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library	https://www.carersuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library/carers-rights-and-entitlements-what-was-new-in-2017-and-what-s-changing-in-2018	NGO	Carers organisations	Carers Rights and Entitlements: What was new in 2017 and what's changing in 2018? 11 December 2017 PDF: file:///C:/Users/ProBook4340s/Downloads/whats-new-and-changing-2017-2018-carers-rights-and-entitlements-december-2017%20(1).pdf This briefing gives professionals an overview of different rights and entitlements across care, health, welfare rights and employment. It is designed to help professionals advising carers review and refresh knowledge of what has changed over the last year and ... Read more....	National	-	-	https://www.carsuk.org/help-and-advice/financial-support/help-with-benefits/carers-allowance	NGO	Carers organisations	Carers Rights and Entitlements What was new in 2017 and what's changing in 2018? PDF SAVED	Y
15.02.18	https://www.carsuk.org/help-and-advice/financial-support/help-with-benefits/carers-allowance	https://www.carersuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library/carers-rights-and-entitlements-what-was-new-in-2017-and-what-s-changing-in-2018	https://www.carersuk.org/help-and-advice/financial-support/help-with-benefits/carers-allowance	NGO	Carers organisations	You may be eligible for Carer's Allowance if you meet all the following conditions: you look after someone who gets a qualifying disability benefit you look after that person for at least 35 hours a week you are aged 16 or over you are not in full-time education you don't earn over £116 a week (after deductions) you satisfy UK presence and residence conditions	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15.02.18	https://www.carsuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library/state-of-caring-in-wales-2017	https://www.carersuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library/state-of-caring-in-wales-2017	https://www.carsuk.org/wales/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-resources-for-professionals/policy-library/state-of-caring-in-wales-2017	NGO	Carers organisations	To mark Carers Rights Day, Carers Wales has released a report on the 'State of Caring in Wales' (2017). Carers in Wales have shared their views and experiences	-	-	-	-	-	-	PDF State of Caring 2017. SAVED	-
15.02.18	young carers legislation wales	Google Search 'young carers legal provisions Wales'	http://www.childrenwales.org.uk/our-work/young-carers/	NGO	Children and young people	Children in Wales' current work in this area includes: Facilitating a Young Carers Network Sitting on Welsh Government working groups to represent young carers Supporting projects to work together to develop activities for young carers Undertaking consultation work for Welsh Government For more information about any of these issues please contact: Lynne Hill, Policy Director, tel: 029 2034 2434, e-mail: lynne.hill@childrenwales.org.uk .	National Wales	Lynne Hill, Policy Director	Lynne Hill, Policy Director, tel: 029 2034 2434, e-mail: lynne.hill@childrenwales.org.uk .	http://www.childrenwales.org.uk/news/news-archive/new-social-services-legislation-come-force-midnight-050416-w/	NGO	Children and young people	-	y

15.02.18	http://www.childreninwales.org.uk/news/news-archive/new-social-services-legislation-come-force-midnight-050416-w/	http://www.childreninwales.org.uk/our-work/young-carers/	http://www.childreninwales.org.uk/news/news-archive/new-social-services-legislation-come-force-midnight-050416-w/	NGO	Children and young people	<p>New social services legislation to come into force at midnight, 05/04/16 [W]</p> <p>The new Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014 will come into force at midnight.</p> <p>It is hoped the Act will see a fairer, stronger and sustainable social services system in Wales.</p> <p>Under the new Act:</p> <p>People will have a voice in how social services assess and meet their needs Individuals will have access to the right support services at the right time Carers will have greater rights Powers will be strengthened to safeguard vulnerable children</p> <p>For more information about the implementation of the new Act visit the Welsh Government website.</p>	National Wales	-	-	http://gov.wales/newsroom/health-and-social-services/2016/160405social-services/?lang=en	Government Welsh	Government Welsh	-	y	
15.02.18	http://gov.wales/newsroom/health-and-social-services/2016/160405social-services/?lang=en	http://www.childreninwales.org.uk/news/news-archive/new-social-services-legislation-come-force-midnight-050416-w/	http://gov.wales/newsroom/health-and-social-services/2016/160405social-services/?lang=en	Government Welsh	Government Welsh	<p>The Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014 radically transforms the way social services are delivered in Wales, ensuring they meet the needs of individuals, giving people a voice in how social services assess and deliver their care and support and ensuring services are sustainable for the future.</p>	National Wales	-	-	-	-	-	-	Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014	-
15.02.18	Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014 young carers	Google Search	https://socialcare.wales/hub/hub-resource-sub-categories/young-carers-and-young-adult-carers	?	Social care	<p>Overview</p> <p>There are approximately 30,000 carers under the age of 25 in Wales. A carer is someone who provides or intends to provide care for an adult or disabled child. According to the 2011 census, Wales has the highest proportion of carers under 18 in the UK.</p> <p>The Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014 brings with it substantial changes to the rights and entitlements of young and young adult carers. These resources, developed by Carers Trust Wales, outline how the Act relates to these carers and what this means for identifying, assessing, and supporting them.</p>	National Wales	-	-	-	-	-	-	Supporting young and young adult carers under the Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014 Resource Powerpoint SAVED	-
15.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	<p>Young Carers and Young Adult Carers presentation: The Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014 brings in new rights and duties for carers. "A person who provides or intends to provide care for an adult or disabled child." 2: The Act requires any person exercising functions under the Act to 'seek to promote well-being' of: People who need care and support; and Carers who need support</p> <p>This includes a new definition of a carer and a duty on local authorities to support carers.</p>	National Wales	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	<p>'When exercising functions under the Act in relation to children who need care and support and child carers who need support... any persons exercising functions under the Act must have due regard to Part 1 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC).'</p>	National Wales	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	<p>Local authorities and local health boards must jointly assess:</p> <p>'The extent to which there are carers in the area of assessment who need support'</p> <p>and</p> <p>'The extent to which there are people whose needs for care and support... are not being met'</p> <p>This must include young and young adult carers.</p>	National Wales	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	<p>'When assessing a young adult carer who is aged between 16 and 25 the assessment must include an assessment of any current or future transitions the carer is likely to make into further or higher education, employment or training.'</p>	National Wales	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

15.02.18	young carers policy wales	Google search	http://gov.wales/topics/health/socialcare/carers/?lang=en	Government Welsh	Government Welsh	1: The latest version of the Carers Strategy for Wales was published in June 2013. 2: o reflect the enhanced rights of carers under the Social Services and Well Being (Wales) Act and set out our main priority areas for supporting them, we are developing a draft Carers Strategic Action Plan. To ensure that we reflect the issues that currently affect carers we will be conducting a consultation. As part of that process a carer and stakeholder event will also take place. The consultation will be launched at the end of September 2017. A statement from the Minister for Social Services and Public Health to update on its progress will be issued on Carers Rights Day – 24th November 2017.	National Wales	-	-	http://gov.wales/docs/dhss/publications/130613strategwen.pdf	Government Welsh	Government Welsh	Cares strategy Wales 2013 SAVED Being updated : 5.7 XXX Article 12 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child gives children and young people the right to say what they think should happen when adults are making decisions that affect them, and to have their opinions taken into account. XXX	n	
15.02.18	young carers policy wales	Google search	http://gov.wales/topics/health/socialcare/carers/young-carers-toolkit/?lang=en	Government Welsh	Government Welsh	Young carers toolkit: This resource is a training aid for health, education, social services professionals, young carers and young adult carers. To compliment this training resource a series of videos have been produced which can be viewed on YouTube (external link) https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLHBVoCVw4XZRxpNi7HbjmMTKSyPFMnNNq	National Wales	Lynne Hill, Policy Director	Film https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RVS6azVJXg&index=2&list=PLHBVoCVw4XZRxpNi7HbjmMTKSyPFMnNNq	http://gov.wales/topics/health/socialcare/carers/young-carers-toolkit/information-and-policies/?lang=en	Government Welsh	Government Welsh	-	-	
15.02.18										https://carers.org/young-adult-carers-wales					n
15.02.18	http://gov.wales/topics/health/socialcare/carers/young-carers-toolkit/information-and-policies/?lang=en	Google search	http://gov.wales/topics/health/socialcare/carers/young-carers-toolkit/information-and-policies/?lang=en	Government Welsh	Government Welsh	1: In April 2016, the Social Services and Well-being (Wales) Act 2014 enabled us to build on the progress achieved under the Carers Measure and further strengthen the commitment to carers . 2: The Act brings with it enhanced rights for carers. For the first time, carers have an equal right to assessment and support as those they care for they no longer need to demonstrate that they provide significant care in order to have their needs assessed, enabling more people to be recognised as a carer they receive the support available to them. While the onus was previously on carers to request an assessment, the Act places a statutory duty on local authorities to proactively inform carers of their right to be assessed, helping to ensure that no one misses out on the opportunities to which they are entitled once an assessment has been completed, if the carer is eligible, the local authority is required to meet those needs identified and put a statutory care plan in place. 3: This will mean young carers have a right to know what services they can have and that all information is up-to-	National Wales	-	-	http://gov.wales/docs/dhss/publications/170315participationency.pdf	Government Welsh	Children and young people	Children;s National participation standards SAVED PDF	y	
15.02.18	https://carers.org/young-adult-carers-wales	Google search	https://carers.org/young-adult-carers-wales	NGO	Carers organisations	There are an estimated 30,000 carers under the age of 25 in Wales. Carers Trust Wales works to help young and young adult carers overcome barriers in life. Going Higher Wales	-	-	-	https://carers.org/news-item/young-adult-carers-receive-helping-hand-starting-university	NGO	Carers organisations			y
15.02.18	https://carers.org/news-item/young-adult-carers-receive-helping-hand-starting-university	Google search	https://carers.org/news-item/young-adult-carers-receive-helping-hand-starting-university	NGO	Carers organisations	-	National Wales	Kieron Rees, Policy and Public Affairs Manager	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

16.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	UN principles (section 7) The Act requires that persons 'exercising functions' under the Act have due regard to the UN Principles for Older Persons (1991) and the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. The 'due regard' duty is an onerous one (considered much more demanding than merely 'having regard'16) and this may well give rise to challenges to NHS and local authority policy changes (of the type that have characterised the obligations under the Equality Act 201017 where a similar 'due regard' duty exists). While there is a certain logic to the Act prioritising the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child – since it has already been given status in Welsh legislation (ie the Rights of Children and Young Persons (Wales) Measure 2011) – it is less obvious why the UN Principles for Older Persons have been given more prominence than the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities – since the Welsh Government has policies on each.18	National Wales	Professor Luke Clements	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	Young carers In general (and unlike the English legislation30) the 2014 Act does not distinguish between the rights of adult carers and those of young carers although there are minor differences in relation to the assessment duty.	National Wales	Professor Luke Clements	-	-	-	-	-	
16.02.18	young carers legal provisions wales	Google Search	http://www.mentalhealthwales.net/carers-strategy-in-wales/	NGO	Health	A New Carers Strategy for Wales: The Carers Strategy for Wales 2013 was largely superseded by the Social Services and Well-being Act (Wales) 2014 which became law 6th April 2016. A new/updated Carers Strategy for Wales is currently under consideration by Welsh Government.	National Wales	-	-	-	-	-	-	